

Improving Collaboration among Civil Society Organizations : Assessing the Risks of Cross-border Open Data Sharing in the Lower Mekong Region

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Abstract

In this paper, we focus on the problem of understanding the risks and benefits of open data publishing, drawing in part on risk management strategies in other fields. We note that while some work has been done on open data risk assessment for government publishers, there is little guidance for civil society organizations (CSOs) who wish to publish open data. To address this, we develop a framework and toolkit that can assist CSOs in conducting risk assessments before sharing or publishing their data, especially in the context of cross-border data sharing. We then conducted a series of interviews with 27 experts to assess our toolkit. They all had a background in open data implementation among CSOs and governments in the lower-Mekong region, where international open data sharing is ongoing. Based on this we recommend several ways in which the toolkit can be applied, as well as opportunities for further research.

Keywords – open data; data sharing; risk assessment; civil society organizations; lower Mekong region.

1 Background

Open data offers many opportunities and promises significant benefits to governments, citizens and businesses. Open data enables accountability, empowers communities, drives economic growth, and even leads to more accurate and better decision-making processes (Janssen, Charalabidis, & Zuiderwijk, 2012; World Bank Group, 2016). However, there are also risks related to publication and use of open data that should be managed (Kucera & Chlapek, 2014). This is especially true in a context where it is not the government, but civil society actors, who are publishing datasets from different sources.

Moreover, in the current interconnected society, cross-border data sharing is something that becomes inevitable. The need for data to facilitate learning, knowledge sharing and collaboration has triggered the establishment of online data-sharing platforms in many

regions around the world. In this study, the Open Development Mekong (ODM) platform is used as an example on how CSOs are using a common platform to support the transparent sharing and analysis of data to improve and inform constructive dialogue and decision making for sustainable and equitable development in their countries.

2 Research Objective

The objective of the research is two fold. First, it aims to develop an open data sharing risk assessment framework that can assist the CSOs in considering the trade-offs between the pros and cons of sharing their data to the public. Second, it examines the risks and opportunities for open data sharing among CSO partners in different countries, specifically in the lower Mekong region.

3 Methodology

The development of the framework consists of two steps. First, a literature review was conducted in order to understand the theoretical approach for building such a framework. Based on the results of the literature review, a risk assessment framework was constructed.

Second, using the ODM network as a case study we tested the applicability of the framework by developing a toolkit for civil society organizations. Regional experts were asked to think about risk factors and mitigation strategies specifically relevant to open data sharing on the ODM platform. In addition, the experts were asked to test and comment on the usability aspect of toolkit. A total of 27 experts with the knowledge of open data implementation in the lower-Mekong region were interviewed in two stages during October - November 2018 and August - September 2019. In the first part, these semi-structured interviews focused on understanding risk factors and mitigation strategies, while the later phase focused on the utility, efficacy, and

areas for improvement in the toolkit. The findings from each of the research steps is described in the following sections.

4 Proposed Framework

Similar to risk management strategies in other fields, the open data sharing risk assessment method also relies on the risk-benefit analysis approach. This approach systematically identifies and manages the risks, while promoting or preserving the benefits that could result from the data-sharing activity (CILP, 2016; Eckartz, Hofman, & Van Veenstra, 2014; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2015). Martim, et. al., (2013) use a similar approach to develop a risk analysis of open data in government (municipal) organizations. However, we note that the reality of CSOs requires a more relevant risk assessment framework.

In this way, the risk assessment process is aimed at ensuring compliance with legal requirements, protection of individual rights and interests, as well as guaranteed data quality. By building a sharing risk assessment framework, CSOs can more effectively anticipate, prevent and manage these emerging “data risks”.

Looking through the lens of risk-benefit approach, our literature review found that the data risk-assessment process would undergo several critical processes. The next subsections present its four key components in more detail.

4.1 Step 1: Identification of the Knowledge Assets

Knowledge assets are data points within a given dataset that are expected to have value, assuming the ability of potential users to leverage that data (Aljafari & Sarnikar, 2009). The identification of the list of data assets is a critical first step to identifying the associated benefits and risks.

Based on the resource-based view (Carlsson, 2003), the approach to identify the knowledge assets in the dataset involves assessing their (1) value (2) rareness and (3) imitability. These three categories were designed to measure competitive advantage provided by the knowledge asset.

Data points can be considered knowledge assets if it fulfills one of above criteria. Therefore, the data publisher needs to understand whether the knowledge of the data point enables users to respond to opportunities or threats in their work (value)? To what extent do other organizations possess the similar knowledge asset (rareness)? Is the knowledge asset costly and difficult to obtain or imitate by other organizations that do not

possess it (imitability)? These are the key guiding questions to help data owners evaluate knowledge assets.

4.2 Step 2: Identification of benefits for each stakeholder

Once the data publisher is able to identify the knowledge assets contained in the dataset (Step 1), the next step is to examine the benefits (or incentives) of sharing these data assets systematically and objectively. The benefits need to be evaluated and understood properly at the outset of any risk management process because after mitigating the risks to match the level of risk, the organization (i.e. data publisher) needs to make a decision on whether it is still acceptable to share the data in light of the identified benefits (CILP, 2016).

Open data sharing might bring benefits internally and externally. Sharing data with other CSOs can help data publishers to recognise the gaps in their dataset, leading to a more resilient and trustworthy dataset. Likewise, the external users can use the data for research, development of public policies, and improvement of their problem-solving capacity. More broadly, data sharing could also support the creation of a new public service, stimulating economic growth and innovation (Attard, Orlandi, Scerri, & Auer, 2015; Janssen, Charalabidis, & Zuiderwijk, 2012)

4.3 Step 3: Identification and quantification of risk variables

Experts have argued that risk management in the field of data governance has suffered from the absence of any consensus on what constitutes risks of data sharing. Hence, there is currently no single comprehensive list of risk factors of data sharing (CILP, 2016; Zuiderwijk & Janssen, 2015). Nevertheless, prior studies have categorised risk factors using broad categories such as technical versus non-technical risks.

4.3.1 Risk Identification

Technical risks consist of the risk factors that affect data quality. It is worth noting that In the literature, there is no agreement on the dimensions that characterize data quality. Many proposals have been made, but no one has emerged above the others and established itself as a standard (Batini, Cappiello, Francalanci, & Maurino, 2009). Yet, some dimensions are universally considered important, constituting the focus of the majority of the proposals. These dimensions include accuracy, completeness, consistency, and timeliness.

Furthermore, with regard to the non-technical factors, there is a strong argument among data protection advocates that data risk management must protect people, and not just data (CILP, 2016). The non-technical factors may be related to political, legal, economic, and social aspects. In contrast to technical

risks, non-technical risks may cause harm to individuals, which can be in the form of physical harm, psychosocial/emotional harm, and economic/financial harm (Engine Room, 2016). Physical harms directly place the data publisher as a target and causes physical damage, while psychosocial/emotional harms cause emotional damage to the data publisher and users. Likewise, economic/financial harm causes damage to personal financial assets.

4.3.2 Risk Quantification

The next step after risk identification is risk quantification using a 3x3 probability-impact matrix as shown in Table 1. For each risk factor identified in step 3, the data publisher will assess the likelihood of occurrence (probability, Pi) and the consequence of risk in terms of what the effect would be if it happens (impact, Gi).

Here, the probability is divided based on percentage of occurrence:

- Low - Assessed as less than or equal to 30% chance of occurrence.
- Medium - Assessed as more than 30%, but less than or equal to 70% chance of occurrence.
- High - Assessed as more than 70% chance of occurrence.

Following the Data Risk Checker (Engine Room, 2016), impact is divided into Minor, Moderate, and Major according to the extent to which the occurrence of the risk affects (i) data quality recovery cost (costs associated with the re-execution of the process from data collection to publication) due to deterioration of data quality and (ii) severity of harm to data quality and individuals/organizations.

- Minor - Low cost of data quality recovery compared to the original cost of data production with/without direct or indirect threats with minor or low emotional, physical, and/or economic impact. These threats may include verbal aggression, temporary psychosocial distress, temporary economic deprivation, discrediting, or temporary organizational or team breakdown.
- Moderate - Moderate cost of data quality recovery with/without direct or indirect threats with medium to high emotional, physical, and/or economic impact. These threats may include denigration, exclusion of access to civic rights, psychosocial distress, loss of reputation, loss of livelihood, economic deprivation, moderate to severe physical injury with temporary or permanent effects on basic life functions. High impact threats also include organizational infiltration, personal

intimidation, persecution, harassment, targeting for rights violations, and organizational or team breakdown.

- Major - High cost of data quality recovery with/without direct threats with catastrophic emotional, physical, and/or economic impact that cannot be mitigated. These threats may include denial of civic rights, detainment, imprisonment, disabling physical injury, or death.

Based on the combination of the probability and impact score, one can obtain the level of criticality for each risk using the equation 1 below (Dani, 2009). The calculation produces three levels of risk criticality: low, medium, high.

$$C_i = P_i \times G_i \quad (1)$$

		Impact (consequence of risk)		
		Minor (1)	Moderate (2)	Major (3)
Probability (Likelihood of occurrence)	Low (1)	1	2	3
	Medium (2)	2	4	6
	High (3)	3	6	9

Table 1. Probability-impact matrix.

Criticality:

- Low (1-2) - monitor, further analysis (if required)
- Medium (3-4)-Further analysis required, Immediate action.
- High (>5) – Immediate action, Stop.

A criticism of the probability-impact matrix is that although it is relatively easy to use, it is also subjective to bias when assessing risk probability. To mitigate this bias, the tool (Appendix 3) provides a guideline to help the assessor. Another technique to reduce subjective bias is to try different “definition techniques” in describing the scale. This can include working with the user(s) to better assess the impacts (minor, moderate, major, or indeed additional categories based on the feedback). The goal is to try different ways of describing the scale to give assessors meaningful frames of reference against which they can estimate the probability of a given risk. At present, a 3x3 matrix is being used, but this can be changed and the scale refined depending on input from users.

4.4 Step 4: Dealing with risks

Rarely can risks be eliminated entirely. Hence, the last step of the risk assessment strategy deals with prioritisation of the risks presenting the greatest threat to data and people, and identification of measures that can

reduce the risk as fully as practicable and prudent in light of the benefits presented by sharing data.

Risk management strategies in information systems can also be classified into three distinct categories, depending on the objective of the strategy (Hall, 2016, p.16).

- Preventive - passive techniques designed to reduce the frequency of occurrence of undesirable events. Preventive controls force compliance with prescribed or desired actions and thus screen out aberrant events.
- Detective - devices, techniques, and procedures designed to identify and expose undesirable events that elude preventive controls. Detective controls reveal specific types of errors by comparing actual occurrences to pre-established standards.
- Corrective - Corrective controls are actions taken to reverse the effects of errors detected by detective controls.

Since it is assumed that the data publisher will not be able to address all the risks at once, it is advisable to prepare a timeline for the mitigation plan (short term, mid-term, and long term). In the case where the risks cannot be mitigated, there has to be a discussion to determine whether to release the data or not.

5 Insights from the field test

This section details insights gathered from the open data practitioners in the Lower Mekong region regarding the proposed framework.

5.1 Knowledge assets

The first challenge is related to the publisher's knowledge of the dataset. The ability to identify knowledge assets contained in the dataset, to envision the benefits of sharing the dataset, and suggest and quantify the risks are all dependent on this particular publisher's trait. For example, to understand the rareness and other key aspects of knowledge assets, the assessor needs to have the knowledge of the dataset including whether other organizations also have similar data. To minimize this challenge, besides the importance of selecting the right assessor with knowledge, a second round of review needs to be conducted by the CSO. They might also assign other team members to review the results of the assessment making final approval.

5.2 Contextual Knowledge

Furthermore, the data is never neutral. It is influenced by the socio-economic and political factors within the context in which it operates. Hence, the assessor is required to have a wide range of contextual knowledge to envision risks and benefits that may materialize when a

particular dataset is shared and used. In the toolkit, examples of possible risk and benefit are given to guide the assessor performing the task at hand. Note that these examples are just a guideline, and the assessor is free to remove the risks that are not relevant to the assessment. They can also add benefits specific to the dataset under review. Overall, although the tool has provided few examples as a general guideline, the purpose of open-ended question is to encourage the assessor to think of specific benefits related to the dataset under review.

5.3 Risks

Likewise, the identification and quantification of the risk factors are the most critical and complex steps in the risk management process as there is no standard of what constitutes risks for open data sharing. Finally, the assessment would also include risk mitigation strategies (Eckartz et al., 2014; Telford & Verhulst, 2016). The goal is to identify measures to prevent risks materializing.

The ODM platform is a unique and significant one. The lack of an open data platform on key development issues in the five countries in the lower Mekong drives the initiative, recognizing that the countries share a common resource and geographical boundaries. Yet, because of differences in the legal and political context of the different countries, sharing of data among countries has inherent risks. There are some uncertainties in terms of security risks when sharing data across the country, both for offline and online means. The absence of legal and administrative frameworks related to data sharing among countries in the lower Mekong region, as well as the differences in the regulations concerning copyright and licensing issues, have adverse impacts on cross-border data sharing.

Furthermore, there are also political risks. Concerns such as state monitoring and political prosecution by authoritarian governments are prominent issues. In some countries at the lower Mekong, an individual might be subjected to political prosecution due to sharing information on sensitive domestic issues.

Table 2. Cross-border open data sharing risks.

Domain	Risk	Description
Legal	The absence of legal frameworks	Unavailability of the legal frameworks that can be used for cross-border data sharing.
	Differences in legal frameworks among countries	Possible violation due to differences in legal frameworks governing copyright and censorship among countries.
Political	State monitoring	Authoritarian governments might

		monitor data communication.
	Political prosecution	An individual might be subject to political persecution by sharing information on sensitive domestic issues.
Technical	Hacking	Private data breach - communication might be intercepted by third parties, which can lead to identity exploitation.
	Low quality dataset	Data available in low quality due to the different formats, duplicated data. Data often comes from unidentified source resulting in low trust in data validity.
Social	Limited understanding of the local context	Exposing partners to risk due to limited understanding of their local context. E.g. Sharing data regarding the Royal family or military junta.
	Language barrier	Most laws and regulations concerning data sharing and privacy only exist in the local language.

Technical issues such as hacking and virus/malware are also quite prevalent as well as quality problems in disclosed datasets. Data is often available in low quality due to different reasons: formats, duplication, or data source issues. In fact, low data quality was a major complaint raised by the open data experts in the lower-mekong region.

The cross-border data sharing is unique in terms of understanding of local context. Limited understanding of the local context might expose CSO partners to risks. Some countries have laws that prohibit sharing of data regarding the royal family or military junta. In addition, there is also a language barrier to understand the local laws and regulations of each country.

5.4 Mitigation strategy

Once risks have been identified, risk mitigation strategies must be formulated. Risk mitigation entails selection of appropriate controls or countermeasures to mitigate each risk. Hence, how can the civil society organisations mitigate the different data sharing risks? The mitigation strategies that we developed from the expert interviews are shown below.

Risk Prevention

- Develop cross-border data sharing framework - The policy makers should consider developing a proposal to establish international or regional legal standards for cross-border access and sharing of data. At the same time, the framework needs to promote interoperability in privacy and data protection.
- Improve knowledge and technical skills to use ICT tools - Without a staff that is fully knowledgeable of the tools and techniques to share data safely, organizations will continue to lack confidence in their ability to protect privacy when disclosing data. CSOs need to create better systems and tools (i.e. metadata, cloud services, etc.) and also improve their knowledge and technical skills to use ICT tools.
- Cross-check data source - Incomplete information about data sources in the metadata presents greater risks as it reduces the quality and prevents further use of the data.
- Use encryption - Encryption scrambles text to make it unreadable by anyone other than those with the encryption keys to decode it. This may be necessary when sharing sensitive information.
- Awareness with whom we share the data. - Data that could be shared should always be included in the category of public data as defined by the law (example, Freedom of Information Law)
- Understand the risks of data sharing. - See the list of cross-border data sharing risks.
- Improve user's understanding of the legal and political context - Build awareness on open data, including understanding of relevant laws.

Risk Detection

- Be alert to virus or malicious softwares - It's important for nonprofits to understand the threats of virus and malicious softwares (malwares). They could slow down or cripple systems, and destroy or alter data.
- Conduct penetration test for Open Development Mekong platform - Penetration testing is a systematic process of probing for vulnerabilities in IT applications and networks. It is also useful in validating the efficacy of defensive mechanisms and determining how well end-users adhere to security policies.

Risk Correction

- Use legal advisory service - The legal expert may provide advice on how to respond to regulatory inquiries, drafting data protection compliance and policies, and defend against enforcement efforts and potential lawsuits.

- Work with data security experts - Data security experts can assist in helping organisations understand and plan for cyber risks to reduce impact of any future data security incident.

6 Conclusion

It is critical that risk management around open data does not continue in the largely *ad hoc*, casual terms that it has evolved into today, although it remains important that the methods remain flexible. Other sectors - for example, finance, civil engineering and environmental management - have seen the development of professional practices of risk management, including specialised research, international and sectoral standards, a common vocabulary, and agreed-upon principles and processes. The same is needed in open data risk management. In some cases, these can be borrowed from areas in which formal risk assessments are better developed, but in others it requires the collaboration of regulators, industry, academics, and civil society to fill important gaps.

This research is an attempt to fill in the gap by proposing a framework that can help open data practitioners link their socio-economic and political contexts in navigating the risks of publishing and sharing their data according to open data principles. While the framework is built on a solid theoretical foundation, the practicality of the toolkit needs more field testing. Hence, it is important to treat both documents as work-in-progress such that further revisions could be made upon the input of users. We note that although the toolkit was tested in a specific region, the framework itself is general enough to be applied elsewhere.

In the end, improving risk management in open data needs a concerted effort from all stakeholders - from data publisher to users. This paper also serves as a call for proposals to come up with new approaches, methods, tools to further improve open data risk assessment, and the development of best practices around the world.

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